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Vocational Aspects of Empowering At-risk VET Students in the Baltic Countries and Norway for Employment and Lifelong Learning

Tütlys, Vidmantas

vidmantas.tutlys@vdu.lt, Vytautas Magnus University

Kaminskienė, Lina

lina.kaminskiene@vdu.lt, Vytautas Magnus University

Tikkanen, Tarja

tarja.tikkanen@uis.no, University of Stavanger

Gerdien-Bruin, Marieke

marieke.bruin@uis.no, University of Stavanger,

Sloka, Biruta

biruta.sloka@lu.lv, University of Latvia

Ümarik, Meril

yumarik@tlu.ee, University of Tallinn

Abstract

This article investigates the ways in which vocational education and training (VET) can enhance social inclusion of young people at-risk, both in terms of combating school dropout and promoting transitions between various (social) learning contexts, such as school-work transition in the Baltic countries and Norway. The study draws on a *socio-ecological approach* (Evans, Waite & Kersh, 2011), emphasising that individuals are learning, developing, and acting in a complex system of various social environments and structures, actors, and interrelationships (Jacobsen & Wilensky, 2006; Evans et al., 2011). A mixed-method study by applying a complementary qualitative and a quantitative methodology had been applied. A qualitative, narrative interview study approach is applied to study at-risk youth in VET schools. The study has been targeted to young people, aged 16-24 years, in VET, identified (by their teachers/school leaders) as student at risk in the VET establishments of the Baltic countries and Norway. Research confirmed that at-risk VET students in the most cases notice and value the empowering provided by the vocational education and work experience. These empowering effects include socialization and finding one's place in society and labour market, acquired trust in themselves, received support from the VET teaching staff and acquired positive and meaningful learning experiences.

Keywords

vulnerable students, empowerment, participation, vocational education and training, factors which support and hinder learning and participation, Baltic countries, Norway

1 Research problem and goal

This study is conducted in the framework of the Baltic Research Programme Project “Vocational education and workplace training enhancing social inclusion of at-risk young people” (No. LT08-2-LMT-K-01-010). The main research goal is to investigate the ways in which vocational education and training (VET) can enhance social inclusion of young people at-risk, both in terms of combating school dropout and promoting transitions between various (social) learning contexts, such as school-work transition in the Baltic countries and Norway. The overall research objectives of this study include: 1) exploring how at-risk young people themselves experience and understand their opportunities, prospects and limitations in the context of VET, and what and how are the institutional factors affecting their prospects; 2) analysing existing best practices, particularly those, which involve innovative approaches, methods, tools for supporting social inclusion and preventing dropout, in VET institution, workplace contexts and by local institutions providing learning opportunities; 3) conducting “Educational Learning Lab intervention” in all partner countries, in order to pilot and evaluate innovative approaches, methods and technology-based tools for supporting both at-risk youth to develop their key skills (vocational and personal) and teachers in VET to advance their instructional approach and practices. This conference paper focuses on the third goal of the study and its outcomes. This article is focused on the findings related to the first research objective.

2 Research methodology and methods

The study draws on a *socio-ecological approach* (Evans, Waite & Kersh 2011), emphasising that individuals are learning, developing, and acting in a complex system of various social environments and structures, actors, and interrelationships (Jacobsen & Wilensky, 2006; Evans et al., 2011). For VET students and apprentices, these environments may comprise parents, teachers, supervisors, peers, as well as digital spaces. The socio-ecological approach serves as a basis for the data analysis, enabling the understanding of the role of various social environments that young people are involved in, their learning trajectories, as well as identifying the factors that enable the development of their competences and sense of agency.

Vocational education and training and work create specific context for the acquisition, enrichment and exploiting of social capital for the NEETs and other socially disadvantaged youth groups. Vocational socialization of youth oriented to employment historically has been one of the fundamental missions of the institutionalised, school-based VET provision since its emergence in the industrial societies since the XIXth century. The potential and capacities of VET in exercising *such vocational socialization* and the content /extent of this socialization are defined by the different arrangements, settings and approaches of curriculum design, organization of theoretical and practical training, pedagogical relationships, guidance and assistance to students. *Autonomy and empowerment* of young people are usually at the centre of focus here, but their attainment involves a lot of contradictions. For example, modular competence-based VET curricula due to its flexibility and practice orientation can be regarded as propaedeutically effective and accessible to at-risk VET students (Mulder, 2017; Pilz et al., 2018) in the same time noticing their shortfalls in providing powerful knowledge and solid future oriented qualifications fostering employability and resilience to labour market shocks (Allais, 2016; Young, 2008; Young & Muller, 2013; Wheelalan, 2017). Similarly, strengthening of *the work-based learning* provision for the at-risk young people can

significantly contribute to their *employability and resilience*, but it also depends on *the quality of involved pedagogical relationship and provision of the individualised pedagogical support and guidance* (Billett, 2016). Here the understanding the perceptions of the empowering influence of VET by the at-risk VET students is particularly important and relevant, in seeking to align VET interventions and measures targeted to the empowerment and resilience of the at-risk students to their life projects and enhance the agency of students in learning, working and development of their capacities.

A mixed-method study by applying a complementary qualitative and a quantitative methodology had been applied. A qualitative, narrative interview study approach (Thomson, 2009) is applied to study at-risk youth in VET schools. The study has been targeted to young people, aged 16-24 years, in VET, identified (by their teachers/school leaders) as student at risk in the VET establishments of the Baltic countries and Norway.

The study executed in Lithuania includes 22 face-to-face and online interviews with at-risk VET students in the 4 VET centres of the country located in Vilnius, Kaunas, Alytus and Smalininkai executed in the period from September 2021 to February 2022, as well as 3 focus groups with VET teachers, social pedagogues and other members of teaching staff in the 3 VET centres located in Vilnius (organised online because of pandemic restrictions), Kaunas (live) and Smalininkai (live) by involving 9 participants in total (6 VET teachers, 2 social pedagogues and 1 psychologist).

In Estonia there were executed 20 online interviews via Zoom with VET students, NEET students (3) all over Estonia in the period from September 2021 to May 2022. There was also held an expert interview with a person working for Youth Guarantee initiative and with a long term experience in studying and working with young people in status of NEET, as well as two focus groups with VET teachers, social pedagogues, internship specialists. Interviews were also done via zoom because of the COVID19 restrictions.

In Latvia there were held 22 face-to-face and online interviews with at-risk VET students in the 3 VET centres in the period from September 2021 to February 2022 and three focus groups with VET teachers, social pedagogues and other members of teaching staff in the 3 VET centres.

In Norway there were held 17 face to face interviews with at-risk VET students in the two VET establishments and two focus groups with VET teachers, social pedagogues and other members of teaching staff. Interview questionnaires include the questions asking to evaluate the role and place of the vocational education and work experiences for the empowerment of at-risk students to learning and employment.

Data analysis process comprised of three phases. First, based on the interview guide, three were identified jointly dimensions in the data, covering aspects in the students' interviews, accounting for hindering and supporting factors for completing VET. Second, the analyses along these dimensions were carried out separately in each country. Finally, the findings were compared across the four countries.

3 Institutional factors of empowerment of at-risk students in the Baltic countries and Norway

Specificities of institutional settings of skill formation systems and VET provision in the countries are to be considered in explaining the differences of factors which support and hinder empowerment of VET students and learners reported by the research participants. Political and institutional attitudes to and approaches of dealing with at-risk and disadvantaged youth in VET in the countries should be also considered here.

Empowerment and social integration of at-risk youth in the VET systems of Baltic countries are strongly influenced by the combination of the market orientation and priorities to fostering employability, provision of the equal access to the school-based public VET system

and efforts in providing systemic support to socially disadvantaged or at-risk young people by referring to the EU strategies of skill formation and employment (Tütlys et al 2022).

For example, initial VET in Lithuania has been regarded as a part of state-funded education. The VET Law declares inclusiveness and accessibility of the provision of training as integral part of the goal of VET provision by stressing that VET should aim „to create conditions for the persons with different needs and abilities to acquire vocational qualification and competencies (...) as well as key skills needed for the self-establishment and competition in the changing labour market, lifelong learning...“ (Lietuvos Respublikos Seimas, 2023). There is also declared goal to create conditions for the recognition of competencies and qualifications acquired in the different ways and to ensure accessibility and quality of VET. The first declared principle of VET system is equal opportunities – VET system is socially just, ensures equality of persons independently from their sex, race, ethnicity, language, social origin and status, religion or beliefs; guarantees access to acquisition of qualification and additional competencies for every person. However, this Law also contains provisions which in some ways narrow or limit the implementation of the above indicated principles and declarations. For example, there is provision concerning the access to state-funded VET, which indicates that state funding of initial VET is limited to the training programmes and pathways leading to the acquisition of the first vocational or professional qualification. It means, that graduates of VET programmes cannot apply for the second and further state-funded vocational training programmes, except applying for the continuing training programmes delegated by the State Employment Service.

Due to the domination of the orientation of VET policies in the Baltic countries to the economic goals related to the competitiveness of human capital and market needs, institutional accessibility of training and support for employment at the national level often is not accompanied with the sufficient social, pedagogical and psychological support because of shortage of teaching auxiliary staff capacities (Tütlys et al 2022). Very often it leads to the stronger reliance of at-risk students on themselves (assuming higher personal responsibility for creating future life), as well as on support from their families, kinship, relatives and friends in the learning and employment contexts. Lack of social support pushes VET students to get employed in unskilled and low-skilled jobs thus compromising the quality of studies and chances of graduation. This risk can hardly be counteracted by still quite fragmented work-based learning opportunities provided by the market-oriented, but school-based VET systems of the Baltic countries.

Empowering and inclusion of youth through VET and lifelong learning pathways are established and important priorities in the VET policy agendas and practices in the Nordic countries, as a part of Nordic welfare state model (Albæk et al, 2015; Anvik and Waldahl, 2017; Follesø, 2015; Frostad et al, 2015; Nilsson, 2010). In case of Norway the VET provision is supported by the well-established and strong social welfare mechanisms, what reduces the need of the support for at-risk students from their families, relatives and friends in the processes of learning and employment, but also weakens development of their autonomy and readiness to assume personal responsibility for learning and employment. Systemic and sustainable accessibility of the work-based learning significantly contributes to increasing the possibilities for such young people to get employed in the skilled job positions.

4 Results, conclusions and recommendations

In general, research confirmed that at-risk VET students in the most cases notice and value the empowering provided by the vocational education and work experience. These empowering effects include socialization and finding one's place in society and labour market, acquired trust

in themselves, received support from the VET teaching staff and acquired positive and meaningful learning experiences. There have been identified country related specificities of these attitudes of students. For example, the students in Lithuania and Latvia tend to stress the empowering effect of VET in contrasting to lack of such empowerment in the general education, as well as indicate the meaningfulness of vocational learning for their future plans. Some students in Estonia indicate the lack of support and significant difficulties in orientation in the VET environment what impedes their empowerment for learning and employment.

Table 1

Factors which support and hinder empowerment and participation of vulnerable students in learning and employment in the Baltic countries and Norway

Factors which support empowerment and participation of vulnerable students in learning and employment			
Lithuania	Latvia	Estonia	Norway
Supportive family relationships. Individualized pedagogical and psychological support from teachers, supervisors and peers in the VET schools (much less in the general education establishments). Meaningful and work-practice related learning with clear objectives, systemic career counselling. Active engagement of the VET students in the students' council activities. Possibilities to develop skills and to get socialized in the international students exchange programmes (Erasmus+).	Supportive family relationships. Personalized socio-pedagogical support from education institution by providing support person (class educator – <i>grupas audzinātājs</i>) who deals with different learning and life problems of students. Possibilities to develop skills and to get socialized in the international students exchange programmes (Erasmus+).	Stable family background and supportive family relations. Flexible VET curricula, which enables meaningful learning and development of key skills. Career counselling delivered by psychologists. Mentoring of vulnerable students (to help students build resilience and prepare them for new independence and responsibilities by helping prepare them for living on their own).	Emotional support from the family and friends. Meaningful learning in the VET school, feeling the relevance of learning and seeking for results. Pedagogical and psychological support from the teachers. Feeling accepted in the workplaces during the apprenticeship training and work-based learning.
Factors which support empowerment and participation of vulnerable students in learning and employment			
Lithuania	Latvia	Estonia	Norway
Unsupportive family relationships. Lack of support from the teachers (experienced in the general education). Learning detached from the work practice. Insufficient volume of practical training. Loneliness at school. Complex pathways of education and acquisition of vocational qualifications	Difficult family situation. Lack of support from the teaching staff. Poverty in the low-income families, especially in the rural areas.	Low interest in the study field; previously experienced school bullying, low self-esteem, depression, anxiety and problems with mental health. Lack of support of teaching staff in the VET schools; lack of creativity in the curriculum.	Unstable and unsupportive family situation. Bullying experience in the previous stages of education. Negative cultural and relational experiences from studying in VET school. Learning irrelevant for the work practice.

<p>defined by the regional differences of labour market and accessibility of VET in the regions (challenge in the rural areas and smaller towns). Poverty and employment in the low-skilled jobs often leading to dropout.</p>		<p>Higher interest in getting general education diploma rather than VET qualification. Difficulties in searching for places for practical training (this responsibility is delegated to students). Employment in low skilled jobs during studies.</p>	<p>Isolation, feeling excluded, bullying experience in the VET establishment. Loneliness and feeling abandoned in the workplace learning settings, lack of support from peers, supervisors and co-workers during the practical training.</p>
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What regards work experience and employment the research disclosed controversial implications of work for the empowerment of at-risk students, especially in the Baltic countries. Some students tend to appreciate the access to practical training in the real work environments offered by the modernized and equipped VET centres in the all countries involved in this study. Students from the rural areas (Lithuania) indicate the shortage of high-quality practical training in the work process, especially what regards experiences of work-based learning. Employment of at-risk students in the low-skilled or unskilled jobs during their studies present significant risk of leaving the studies because of workload and lack of time for studies (Lithuania, Estonia), while some employed students. Although students recognize that the main reason of such employment is necessity to find the source of subsistence for themselves and material support for their families, some of them outline the positive impact of such work experience for their self-esteem and for development of personal work ethics.

These research findings have important implications for VET policy learning and development of policies and practices targeted to empower vulnerable VET students. First of all, they disclose that despite of the differences of the institutional settings of the VET provision, VET teaching staff remains a central factor of support for such students in the all countries. This implies necessity to ensure the availability of sufficient volume of VET teaching staff and their capacities to deal with the challenges and problems of the vulnerable VET students, what remains a significant challenge in some of the countries, involved in this research study, like Lithuania. Secondly, work-based learning and apprenticeship rather expectedly emerges as significant factors which supports learning and participation of the vulnerable students in the all countries involved in this study, which could potentially become a remedy against dropping-out caused by unskilled and low-skilled employment of these students during their studies in the Baltic countries. Again, the main challenge here is to expand accessibility of quality apprenticeships for the vulnerable learners, what requires significant efforts from the policy makers, social partners and VET providers.

5 Disclaimer

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Biographical notes

Vidmantas Tūtlys is professor of Education Science and Researcher at Vytautas Magnus University Institute of Educational Research in Kaunas, Lithuania. His research areas cover development of vocational education and training policies, VET curriculum design, skill formation and qualification systems.

Lina Kaminskienė is Chancellor of the Academy of Education, Professor of Education Science and Researcher at Vytautas Magnus University Institute of Educational Research in Kaunas, Lithuania. Her research interests include social partnership in VET, leadership in education.

Tarja Tikkanen is professor in Education, Department of Education and Sports Science (Teacher Education), University of Stavanger. Tarja Tikkanen is an internationally renowned researcher investigating lifelong learning in the context of working life. Within this wide scope, major topics for her research have been: job-related competence (skills, knowledge, attitudes) in general, and in the context of the digital transformation and technology-rich work environments, in particular; participation in job-related learning, and; organisational learning and leadership from a learning organization perspective. She has been exploring these issues from different perspectives and within different sectors (private and public enterprises, such as kindergartens, schools, also trade unions).

Marieke Bruin currently works at the Department of Education and Sports Science, University of Stavanger (UiS) as an associate professor. Marieke does research in educational science. Her latest project is 'Parents' Experiences on Follow-up of Children's Language Learning after Cochlear Implantation.'

Biruta Sloka is professor at the University of Latvia. Ms Sloka is also President of Association of Latvia's Statisticians, Member of Statistics Council of Republic of Latvia as well as part of scientific committees of international conferences and editorial boards of several scientific journals. She was leading EuroFaculty Riga centre (an international project of Council of Baltic Sea States – CBSS) and was advisor to six ministers of economy and two ministers of education and science.

Meril Ümarik is associate professor at the Tallinn University, School of Education Sciences. Her research interests cover VET teachers work and agency, professionalism of VET teachers, development of VET systems in Estonia and post-socialist countries.